

3D Topology Optimization for Composite Sandwich Structures by the Coating Approach

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Background

Traditional composite structures

Source: NLR-TP-2016-201

Source: custom-composite.com

Additive manufacturing

3dhubs.com

Complex self-stiffened structures

Soluble core

Liquid molded panel

Stiffened panel

Lehnert, Master's thesis, McGill (2019)

stratasys.com

Problematic

Design of non-standard stiffened structures

- Highly complex task
- Limitations of existing design tools
 - Sizing optimization
 - Shape optimization
 - Topology optimization

Solution:

- Develop topology optimization for composite materials

Overview of topology optimization for composite structures

Approach	Continuous fibre angle	Multi-material	Lamination parameters
Design variables	ρ_i & $\theta_i, \quad \forall i \in \Omega$	$\rho_i^j, \quad j = 1..n_c \text{ \& \; } \forall i \in \Omega$	ρ_i & $V_i^j, \quad \forall i \in \Omega \text{ \& \; } j = 1..12$
Optimization scheme	<i>Simultaneous or sequential</i>	<i>Simultaneous</i>	<i>Sequential</i>
Example	<p>1st step Post processing steps</p> <p>Peeters et al. (2015)</p>		

- Limited to 2D problems
- Handles material orientations through additional design variables
- Poor control on manufacturability of the solution, no experimental demonstration/evaluation

Project objectives

1. Develop a 3D topology optimization approach for sandwich structures with anisotropic shells
 - Assume laminate properties are known a priori (constant stiffness and thickness)
 - Core has constant relative density
2. Develop an approach to approximate local material orientations based on the manufacturing process
 - Fabric draping
 - Material extrusion additive manufacturing
3. Conduct an experimental benchmark for AM structures optimized for minimum compliance
 - Isotropic vs the developed anisotropic approach

Methodology

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Formulation of the topology optimization problem

Minimize compliance :

$$C = \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{U}$$

Subject to :

$$\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{U} = \mathbf{F}$$

$$g(\mathbf{x}) = V(\mathbf{x}) - v_f V_{tot} \leq 0$$

$$0 \leq x_{min} \leq x_i \leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, Ne$$

Finite element stiffnesses:

$$\mathbf{k}_{lam,i} = \int \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D}_i(x_i, \mathbf{D}_{lam}, \{\mathbf{e}'_1, \mathbf{e}'_2, \mathbf{e}'_3\}_i) \mathbf{B} d\Omega$$

$$\mathbf{k}_{core,i} = \int \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D}_i(x_i, \mathbf{D}_{core}) \mathbf{B} d\Omega$$

Two-step filtering approach with local material orientations

1st filtering step

x

$R_1 \downarrow$

$$-r_1^2 \nabla^2 \hat{x} + \hat{x} = x$$

\hat{x}

$\alpha, \beta \downarrow$

$$\varphi = \frac{\tanh \beta_1 \eta_1 + \tanh \beta_1 (\hat{x} - \eta_1)}{\tanh \beta_1 \eta_1 + \tanh \beta_1 (1 - \eta_1)}$$

2nd filtering step

φ

$R_2 \downarrow$

$$-r_2^2 \nabla^2 \hat{\varphi} + \hat{\varphi} = \varphi$$

$\hat{\varphi}$

$\|\nabla \hat{\varphi}\|_\alpha$

$\alpha, \beta \downarrow$

$$\|\nabla \hat{\varphi}\|_\alpha = \frac{1}{\alpha} \sqrt{\frac{\partial \hat{\varphi}^2}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \hat{\varphi}^2}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \hat{\varphi}^2}{\partial z}}$$

τ

$$\tau = \frac{\tanh \beta_2 \eta_2 + \tanh \beta_2 (\|\nabla \hat{\varphi}\|_\alpha - \eta_2)}{\tanh \beta_2 \eta_2 + \tanh \beta_2 (1 - \eta_2)}$$

- Void ($\varphi = 0$)
- Core ($\varphi = 1, \tau = 0$)
- Shell ($\tau = 1$)

Density interpolation:

$$\rho_{phys} = \rho_c \varphi + (\rho_s - \rho_c \varphi) \tau$$

Local orientations in shell:

$$\|\nabla \hat{\varphi}\|_\alpha \neq 0 \rightarrow \nabla \hat{\varphi} \perp \text{shell} \rightarrow \theta(\nabla \hat{\varphi})$$

$$D_{phys} = D_c \varphi^p + (D_s(\theta) - D_c \varphi^p) \tau^p$$

Ref.: Clausen A., Aage N., and Sigmund O. (2015)

Approximation approach for local material orientations in 3D problems

Extrusion AM process:

Approximation approach of the local extrusion orientations:

Local routine:

1. Find tangent plane from e_3
2. Select intersecting plane
3. Calculate $e_1, e_2 = f(\nabla \hat{\phi})$
4. Transform stiffness tensor

Resulting distribution of local extrusion orientations

Optimization flow chart

Results

- Design of a composite stiffened panel
- Experimental benchmark using extrusion additive manufactured MBB beams

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Composite stiffened panel problem

Load = -10 N

Max sandwich thickness = 20 mm

Shell laminate = 1 mm, Cross-ply $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$

Base laminate = 2 mm, Quasi-iso $[0^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$

Mesh : 600 x 600 x 80 (28.8 M hex elements)

E_1	E_2	E_3	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}
10 GPa	5 GPa	5 GPa	0.25	0.25	0.4	2.5 GPa	2.5 GPa	2 GPa

Specific gravity: 1.2

Triangular honeycomb core ($SG = 1.44$, $E_{core,s} = 10$ GPa, $\nu = 0.25$)

Effect of base structure filter radius size

Volume fraction = 30%, Core rel. Density = 30%

$R_1 = 1.5, C = 261.4$

Bottom

45° cut-plane

$R_1 = 2.0, C = 272.5$

$R_1 = 2.5, C = 295.7$

- Manufacturability controlled by proper selection of R_1 and v_f
- Trade-off between performance & manufacturability

Low v_f solution

$v_f = 15\%, R_1 = 2.5, C = 410.7$

Experimental benchmark using extrusion additive manufactured MBB beams

Material characterization

Topology optimization

Isotropic vs orthotropic solutions

Fabrication & testing

Topology optimization solutions to the MBB problem

Benchmark study

Case	Volume fraction (v_f)	First filter radius (R_1)	Shell thickness ($t_s = 0.4R_2$)
1	15%	10 mm	1.5 mm
2	30%	10 mm	1.5 mm
3	15%	20 mm	1.5 mm
4	30%	20 mm	1.5 mm
5	15%	10 mm	1.0 mm
6	30%	10 mm	1.0 mm

Numerical results

Case 1

Post-treatment

Load deflection curves for case 1 solutions

$v_f = 15\%$
 $R_1 = 10 \text{ mm}$
 $t_{\text{shell}} = 1.5 \text{ mm}$

Case 1 - Isotropic

Case 1 - Orthotropic

Experimental benchmark – Summarized results

Case	Bending stiffness [N/mm]			Maximum load [N]			Maximum displacement [mm]		
	Iso	Orth	Difference	Iso	Orth	Difference	Iso	Orth	Difference
1	457	437	4.4%	1282	2580	50.3%	3.3	6.6	49.8%
2	679	623	8.2%	4006	3781	5.6%	7.1	6.6	6.5%
3	316	294	7.0%	1226	1122	8.4%	4.1	4.0	3.2%

Case	Bending stiffness [N/mm]			Maximum load [N]			Maximum displacement [mm]		
	Iso	Orth	Difference	Iso	Orth	Difference	Iso	Orth	Difference
4	512	526	2.7%	3741	4486	16.6%	9.1	11.9	23.5%
5	291	391	25.6%	1779	2586	31.2%	7.7	7.7	0.2%
6	436	442	1.4%	1836	3368	45.5%	4.9	10.0	50.7%

Conclusions

- The new parameterization opens new design opportunities for composite sandwich structures using topology optimization.
- Manufacturability of the solution requires proper selection of the topology optimization parameters.
- Accounting for material anisotropy improved load bearing capacity of the optimized designs.

Future work

- Apply method to broader sets of problems (buckling stability, combined loads, etc.)
- Include modeling approaches to improve local material orientation approximations.
- Improve modelling of the laminate.
- Concurrent optimization of material orientations.

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